

Data Montage: Towards Coherence in Multimodal Data Representation

Sara Akhlaq

sara.akhlaq@fh-potsdam.de

@alltheakhlaq

Arran Ridley

arran.ridley@fh-potsdam.de

@arranarranarran

Mark-Jan Bludau

mark-jan.bludau@fh-potsdam.de

@markiaaan

Marian Dörk

marian.doerk@fh-potsdam.de

@nrchtct

Multimodal Data Representations

Montage of Attraction

A way of combining different visuals and sounds in order to evoke associations and comparisons in a film

Molecular Units

According to montage of attraction, an effective theatrical performance comprises heterogeneous components that, while maintaining their meaningful individuality, when fused offer a deeply engaging and emotionally stimulating experience

Organic Unity

Data Montage

Careful interweaving of perceptual variables in multimodal interfaces

elevated emotional
impact from the
interweaving of
modalities, the
subject matter,
and the underlying
data

Data Montage Exemplars

	Visualization	Sonification	Auralization	Olfaction	Edibalization	Physicalization
Tied in Knots	■	□	■	□	□	□
COVID Death Toll	■	■	□	□	□	□
Eyes	■	■	□	□	□	■
Data Cuisine	■	□	□	□	■	■
Commute	■	■	□	□	□	□
Histogramy	■	■	□	□	□	□
50 Years Swiss Music Charts	■	■	■	□	□	□
Silent Cries of China's Depressed Netizens	■	■	□	□	□	□
Der Sound zum Tiefen Fall der SPD	■	■	□	□	□	□
Way of Curating	■	□	■	□	□	□
Reconstructing Seven Days of Protests	■	□	■	□	□	□
Museum of the World	■	■	□	□	□	□
Smellmap of Paris	■	□	□	■	□	□

Coronavirus: How can we imagine the scale of Covid's death toll?

By the BBC Visual and Data Journalism team | 7 December 2020 | Coronavirus

The suffering from the coronavirus pandemic has come to define 2020. But how do you grasp the immense scale of loss?

Flowers - symbols of grief, peace, and love - serve as a tribute to those who have died.

Imagine this pandemic as a **flower**. In the animation below, the **stem** grows as Covid-19 cases increase over time and the **petals** unfurl as more people die with the disease.

Automatic animations on

29 September

33,649,775 cases

1,008,688 deaths

Click the **sound button** to hear the pandemic represented in audio.

The world was firmly in the grip of Covid-19 by April, as the growing petals in this animation show. Then, despite restrictions introduced by many countries, the wave of daily deaths worldwide dipped only slightly.

The number of daily deaths started climbing again at the end of summer in the northern hemisphere. And the petals representing the most recent data are the largest of all, showing that the number of daily deaths around the world is higher now than it has ever been.

Redundant encoding

Blurred boundaries between modalities

Emotional response

Beyond what meets the eyes, ears, and hands

Thank you!

Questions?